

Resistance of recommended and traditional varieties to gall midge (GM)

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Resistance to rice GM *Orseolia oryzivora* H & G was tested in the field at Edozhigi, Nigeria, during the 1984 wet season. Ten recommended and 10 traditional varieties were planted in four 10-hill rows, 15- $\times$ 20-cm spacing, with 3 replications. Susceptible check FARO 13 was planted every 20 rows. Plots were fertilized to induce tillering. Number of onion shoots among total tillers was assessed 45 d after transplanting. The tillers were clipped to induce fresh tillering and reinfestation damage assessed at 25 d after clipping. Rating was by the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

All entries were damaged (see table). Seven traditional and 3 recommended varieties recorded less than 5% damage. $\mathcal{S}$

Gall midge damage at Edozhigi, Nigeria, 1984 wet season.

Variety	Onion shoots ^a (%)	Reaction ^b
<i>Traditional</i>		
Farin Karuwa	7.3	5
Dan Maizadum	0.6	1
Jan Iri Gari	1.5	3
Babu Rashi	6.4	5
Dan Manu	3.9	3
Dan Sakutaman	16.2	7
Dan Gyanga	1.2	3
Dan Dauda	0.3	1
Abraka Kwambe	5.4	3
Jatau	3.4	3
<i>Improved</i>		
FARO 15	6.3	5
FARO 27	7.9	5
FARO 29	7.5	5
FARO 11	6.1	5
FARO 8	5.6	5
FARO 7	2.9	3
FARO 14	4.2	3
FARO 26	2.2	3
FARO 19	8.7	5
FARO 13	18.0	7

^aMean of 6 replications. ^bResistance rating where 0 = no damage, 1 = resistant, 3 = moderately resistant, 5 = moderately susceptible, 7 = susceptible, and 9 = highly susceptible.

Genetic evaluation against rice brown planthopper (BPH) at Cuttack

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Part of the nearly 20,000 rice germplasm accessions available at CRRI was systematically evaluated in 1975-80 using BPH 1st-instar nymphs mass-reared in the greenhouse. About 700 CRRI accessions (AC), 350 Assam rice collections (ARC), 50 Manipur Rice collections (MNP), 50 Jeypore Botanical Survey Collections (JBS), and 100 others were screened using the free-choice seedling bulk screening technique and scored on the 0-9 scale of the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

Of 1,250 rices screened, 59 cultivars and 15 cultures were resistant (see table). Among them are 31 AC, 20 ARC, 1 MNP, 1 JBS, and 6 from other sources. Of these, 12, (ARC14529, ARC14766, ARC14766-A, ARC10550, ARC14342, AC3376, AC3747, Ptb 19, Ptb 21, Ptb 33, T1415, T1426) had been reported resistant in different parts of India. The rest are newly identified potential donors. $\mathcal{S}$

Rices identified resistant to BPH at Cuttack.

AC7, AC33, AC34, AC94, AC108, AC131, AC199, AC255, AC357, AC369, AC424^a, AC562, AC577, AC578, AC584, AC592, AC595, AC596, AC600, AC608, AC618, AC1125, AC1165, AC1224^a, AC1364, AC1373, AC1619, AC1771, AC3090, AC3376, AC3747

ARC1017-6^a, ARC5984, ARC7289, ARC10176^a, ARC10550, ARC12627^a, ARC14342^a, ARC14529^b, ARC14729, ARC14736, ARC14766^b, ARC14766-A^a, ARC14810, ARC15223^a, ARC15228, ARC15284, ARC15821, ARC15831^a, ARC18529

MNP76

JBS770

PTB10, PTB21, PTB33, T1415, T1425, T1426
CR157-392-175, CR57-MR 1523^a, CR94-MR 1550 (white)^a, CR157-393-107, CR157-392-41-112^a, IR2071-636-5-5, IR801-3-5-2, IR2070-439-3-4-3, IR2070-439-6-5, ORSJR 214, CR157-392-11-4, CR157-392-107-175^a, CR157-389-12-90^a, CR157-389-43-120^a, S11-52-626^a

^aDamage score of 1.1 to 2.0. ^bDamage score of 0.1 to 1.0.

IET6012 (ACM8) — a promising gall midge-resistant rice culture

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Since 1983, 60 genotypes of rice received from the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project have been screened for gall midge (GM)

resistance by growing them under unprotected conditions in the endemic area. IET6012, IET7250, and Surekha were found resistant to GM under laboratory and field conditions. IET6012 (ACM8) is a medium-duration variety (120 d) with fine grain and high yield potentials. It has yielded an average of 4.9 t/ha, 26% more than IR20 (see table). IET6012 (ACM8) was relatively free from GM incidence. $\mathcal{S}$

Performance of GM-resistant cultures in Tamil Nadu, India.

Entry	Parentage	Days to 50% flowering	Mean yield (t/ha) under unprotected conditions	Panicle length (cm)	Reaction to GM	
					Greenhouse (0-9)	Field (% silvershoots)
IET6012 (ACM8)	IR8/W1263	88	4.9	19.64	0	Nil
IET7250	RP348/ARC6079	105	4.2	17.72	3	Nil
Surekha	—	113	2.7	21.64	0	Nil
Co 37	TN1/Co 29	89	3.8	20.08	7	27.6
IR20	IR262/TKM6	108	3.9	18.06	7	27.4